

Supplemental Information for:

Historic museum samples reveal hybrid origin of an extinct crater lake endemic embedded in a background of multi-species gene flow

Amy R. Tims, Peter J. Unmack, Michael P. Hammer, Culum Brown, Mark Adams, Matthew D. McGee

Table of Contents:

Supplementary File S1	p. 3	Description of testing for linkage disequilibrium in our data. Plots of similarity between LD-filtered and LD-unfiltered STRUCTURE results, and STRUCTURE results of the LD-filtered dataset at k=3.
Supplementary File S2	p. 5	Table showing the number of individuals and loci in SNP data sets after applying different filtering thresholds and parameters.
Supplementary File S3	p. 6	ASTRAL and STRUCTURE results for all 389 individuals in the dataset.
Supplementary File S4	p. 7	A plot of mean natural log probability of the data for different values of K across the six data subsets. All models suggest that there is little model improvement above K = 3.
Supplementary File S5	p. 8	Map of the study region including locality names
Supplementary File S6	pp. 9-12	STRUCTURE results for the 32 retained populations and k-values of 2 through 5.
Supplementary File S7	pp. 13-18	STRUCTURE results for the 32 retained populations and k=3 with six different filtering parameters
Supplementary File S8	pp. 19-22	Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between <i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i> and <i>M. sp. "Malanda"</i> . Different possibilities of the origins of the Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations are presented.
Supplementary File S9	p. 23	Evidence for separate histories of Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations.
Supplementary File S10	p. 24	ABBA-BABA test results showing excess allele sharing with <i>M. sp. "Malanda"</i> populations in the Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations, and in three individuals from the Molo Creek population.

Supplementary File S11	pp. 25-27	Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like” and <i>M. splendida</i> . Six graphs are presented, showing the best graphs found when different numbers of admixture events were modelled (0-5).
Supplementary File S12	pp. 28-30	Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between <i>M. sp.</i> “Malanda” and <i>M. splendida</i> . Six graphs are presented, showing the best graphs found when different numbers of admixture events were modelled (0-5).
Supplementary File S13	pp. 31-32	Further discussion of Tablelands rainbowfish diversity and admixture.
Supplementary File S14	pp. 33-35	Unique variants in Lake Eacham and other populations found with fixed difference analysis. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Table showing the number of fixed differences found in each population and its statistical significance. - Table showing the coverage of unique variants in the Lake Eacham and Lake Euramoo populations.

Supplementary File S1: Exploring linkage disequilibrium

We mapped SNP reads to the genome of *Melanotaenia duboulayi*, the most closely related rainbowfish species for which an annotated genome is available, using bbmap (Bushnell, 2014) to affirm that our panel of SNPs were randomly and evenly distributed across the genome. Of the 13767 SNPs retained in our least stringently filtered dataset (filtered by 80% coverage, no filter for MAF), 10984 SNPs could be mapped to the *M. duboulayi* genome. We identified all pairs of SNPs within 10kbp of each other and performed linkage disequilibrium tests using the 'ld' function from the genetics package in R v 4.1.3. A total of 5440 pairwise tests were performed. A total of 156 pairwise tests yielded R^2 values of 0.2 or greater, and one SNP in each of these pairs was randomly selected to be discarded. As some SNPs were compared against multiple nearby SNPs, a total of 151 unique SNPs were discarded to form our LD-filtered dataset, leaving a total of 13616 SNPs.

Five iterations of STRUCTURE were run on the LD-filtered dataset with $K=3$. The admixture and uncorrelated allele frequency models were applied with no population prior estimate. Results were highly consistent between individual STRUCTURE runs. We then compared the average STRUCTURE result of the LD-filtered dataset with the LD-unfiltered dataset run with the same parameters. Population assignments were all within 0.63% of the LD-unfiltered results, and were on average within 0.05%. Because of the similarity between results regardless of LD-filtering, we elected to use an LD-unfiltered dataset in subsequent analyses to retain as much genetic information as possible.

Plots showing the relationship between individual population assignments in average STRUCTURE results of LD-filtered and LD-unfiltered datasets. The population assignments varied very little regardless of whether LD filtering was performed ($R^2 > 0.999$). Individuals STRUCTURE runs on each dataset were also highly consistent.

STRUCTURE results for the 32 retained populations and k = 3 when filtered for coverage and low linkage disequilibrium in SNPs closer than 10kbp apart. Filtering for LD had little effect on the admixture proportions recovered.

filters: 80% coverage; 10kbp LD < 0.2

Supplementary File S2: Table showing the number of individuals and loci in SNP data sets after applying different filtering thresholds and parameters.

Filtering process	Number of individuals	Number of loci
Pre-filtering – all informative markers	234	23502
80% coverage across loci and individuals	232	13767
80% coverage across loci and individuals; minimum allele frequency 1%	232	8559
90% coverage across loci and individuals	229	10207
90% coverage across loci and individuals; minimum allele frequency 1%	229	6193
95% coverage across loci and individuals	227	7759
95% coverage across loci and individuals; minimum allele frequency 1%	227	4689

Supplementary File S3: ASTRAL and STRUCTURE results

ASTRAL plot (left) shows estimated relationships of 389 individuals based on silicoDArT data. STRUCTURE plot (right) shows genetic structure for k=3 based on SNP data. Populations retained for Admixtools analyses are labelled and individuals' names written in black. Individuals dropped from Admixtools analyses are in grey. Three individuals from the Molo Creek Tributary population excluded in some analyses due to low-level admixture signal are denoted with an asterisk (*).

Supplementary File S4: A plot of mean natural log probability of the data for different values of K across the six data subsets. Across all data subsets, models suggest that there is little improvement in model fit above K = 3.

Supplementary File S5: Map of the study region including locality names and numbers.

Supplementary File S6: STRUCTURE results for the 32 retained populations and k-values of 2-5.

Results are based on the SNP dataset filtered by 95% coverage and 1% MAF.

Group.1 Group.2 Group.3

Group.1 Group.2 Group.3 Group.4

Group.1 Group.2 Group.3 Group.4 Group.5

Supplementary File S7: The effect of different filtering parameters on STRUCTURE results.

STRUCTURE results for the 32 retained populations and $k = 3$ under the different filtering parameters listed in Supplementary File S1 are shown. Applying different levels of filtering had little effect on the admixture proportions recovered.

filters: 95% coverage

M. 'eachamensis-like' M. 'Malanda' M. splendida

filters: 90% coverage; 1% MAF

■ M. 'eachamensis-like'
 ■ M. 'Malanda'
 ■ M. splendida

filters: 90% coverage

M. 'eachamensis-like' M. 'Malanda' M. splendida

filters: 80% coverage; 1% MAF

■ M. 'eachamensis-like'
 ■ M. 'Malanda'
 ■ M. splendida

filters: 80% coverage

M. 'eachamensis-like' M. 'Malanda' M. splendida

Supplementary File S8: Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between *M. "eachamensis-like"*- and *M. sp. "Malanda"*.

Possible evolutionary relationships between populations of *M. sp. "Malanda"* and *M. sp. "eachamensis-like"* when no admixture events are modelled. The populations of hybrid origin, Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek, are sometimes resolved as closer to pure *M. sp. "Malanda"* populations, and sometimes closer to *M. sp. "eachamensis-like"* populations. Models that do not allow for admixture are a significantly worse fit to the data (higher likelihood scores) than modelled population histories including admixture.

0 reticulations
score = 1184.8

0 reticulations
score = 1193.6

Best returned admixture graphs for one and two admixture events, excluding the Molo Creek tributary population with low-level admixture. Although the graph with two admixture events is a slightly better fit to the data (lower likelihood score), this difference was not significant when we applied bootstrapping with the 'compare_fits' function ($p > 0.05$).

1 reticulation
score = 19.8

2 reticulations
score = 12.3

Best returned admixture graphs for two and three admixture events, including all individuals from the Molo Creek tributary population. The graph with three admixture events is a better fit to the data (lower likelihood score), but this difference was not significant when we applied bootstrapping with the 'compare_fits' function ($p > 0.05$).

2 reticulations
score = 21.7

3 reticulations
score = 13.5

Best returned admixture graphs for one and two admixture events, including only the unadmixed individuals from the Molo Creek tributary population. The graph with two admixture events is a significantly better fit to the data than the single admixture graph ($p = 0.014$).

1 reticulation
score = 31.5

2 reticulations
score = 15.1

Supplementary File S9: Evidence for separate histories of Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations

There is some evidence to suggest the Dirran Creek population originated from an independent hybridisation event, rather than sharing a single origin with the Lake Eacham population.

1. Geographic separation

There is significant geographic isolation between the two populations, and the lack of *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like”-derived genetic signal in intervening populations (Figure 2) means it is unlikely the two populations are derived from a single hybrid source population.

2. Admixture graph fit

When Admixtools was run on filtered population subsets including only Dirran Creek, Lake Eacham and pure *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like” and *M. sp.* “Malanda” populations, bootstrapped results suggested that a two-event scenario more closely aligned with the SNP data than a one-event scenario. This was true both when the Molo Creek tributary population was excluded completely, and when only pure individuals from this population were included. When the admixed individuals from Molo Creek tributary were included, a three-event model was a better fit to the data than a two-event model.

3. STRUCTURE results

STRUCTURE results with $K=4$ (Supplementary File S3) cause *M. sp.* “Malanda” to split into two distinct lineages. The proportions of these two lineages present in the Dirran Creek population closely mirror the proportions observed in the Wallace Road population of *M. sp.* “Malanda”, while the proportions seen in the Lake Eacham population are different, and do not directly correspond to any extant *M. sp.* “Malanda” populations. These observations are congruent with the relationships recovered in the Admixtools graphs

4. Morphological differences

There are morphological differences between the Dirran Creek and Lake Eacham populations, particularly with regard to the dorsal and anal fins, which are taller and differently shaped in Dirran Creek fish (Allen, 1989).

References

Allen, G. R. (1989). Lake Eacham rainbowfish rediscovered? *Fishes of Sahul*, 5, 217–219.

Supplementary File S10: ABBA-BABA test results showing excess allele sharing with *M. sp.* “Malanda” populations in the Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations, and in three individuals from the Molo Creek tributary population.

D-statistics, also called ABBA-BABA tests, are a simple way to test for hybridisation. Populations W and X are sister lineages, while population Y may be introgressing with either W or X. Population Z is an outgroup. In the absence of hybridisation, the number of discordant SNPs grouping W and Y together should roughly equal the number grouping X and Y together, and the D statistic will roughly equal zero. Positive scores suggest excess allele sharing between populations W and Y, while negative scores suggest excess allele sharing between populations X and Y. The z-score measures the number of standard errors that the D statistic deviates from 0. An absolute z-score of 3 or more is generally accepted as significant.

Below, we list the combinations of populations used to compute D statistics. The populations were selected based on the above Admixtools graphs suggesting likely patterns of relatedness. D statistics were computed using the ‘qpstat’ function in the Admixtools R package. Significant z-scores are written in bold.

W	X	Y	Z	D-stat	z-score
Lake Euramoo	Lake Eacham museum samples	Wallace Road, Thiaki Creek tributary	<i>M. trifasciata</i> outgroup	-0.61	-26.2
Lake Euramoo	Lake Eacham museum samples	Wallace Road, Thiaki Creek tributary, Molo Creek tributary (unadmixed individuals only)	<i>M. trifasciata</i> outgroup	-0.61	-25.8
Lake Euramoo	Dirran Creek	Wallace Road	<i>M. trifasciata</i> outgroup	-0.63	-20.5
Thiaki Creek	Molo Creek tributary (all individuals)	Charappa Creek, South Johnstone, Lake Euramoo	<i>M. trifasciata</i> outgroup	-0.18	-6.22
Thiaki Creek	Molo Creek tributary (unadmixed individuals only)	Charappa Creek, South Johnstone, Lake Euramoo	<i>M. trifasciata</i> outgroup	-0.068	-2.01

Supplementary File S11: Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like” and *M. splendida*. The best graphs found for different numbers of admixture events (0-5) after 10 admixtools runs are presented below, showing possible evolutionary relationships between populations of pure *M. splendida*, pure *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like”, and admixed *M. splendida*-“eachamensis-like”. Each graph is labelled with the number of admixture events and the model’s score. A lower score suggests that the model fits the data better.

When no admixture events are modelled, the *M. splendida*-introgressed populations of *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like” are the earliest branching lineages, while the one majority-*splendida* introgressed population appears most closely related to the Beatrice River population of *M. splendida*. As more admixture events are modelled, populations with lower admixture proportions are highlighted in the graphs. Admixture results are broadly consistent with STRUCTURE results (Supplementary File S2).

0 reticulations
score = 1977

1 reticulation
score = 865.4

2 reticulations
score = 344

3 reticulations
score = 135.5

4 reticulations
score = 93.7

5 reticulations
score = 53.4

Supplementary File S12: Admixtools admixture graphs showing admixture between *M. sp.* “Malanda” and *M. splendida*. The best graphs found for different numbers of admixture events (0-5) after 10 admixtools runs are presented below, showing possible evolutionary relationships between populations of pure *M. splendida*, pure *M. sp.* “Malanda”, and admixed *M. splendida*-“Malanda”. Each graph is labelled with the number of admixture events and the model’s score. A lower score suggests that the model fits the data better.

When no admixture events are modelled, the *M. splendida*-introgressed populations of *M. sp.* “Malanda” are the earliest branching lineages, while the majority-*splendida* introgressed populations are spread through the *M. splendida* portion of the graph. As more admixture events are modelled, populations with lower admixture proportions are highlighted in the graphs. Admixture results are broadly consistent with STRUCTURE results (Supplementary File S2).

0 reticulations
score = 4124.5

1 reticulation
score = 2795.5

2 reticulations
score = 2239.6

3 reticulations
score = 1112.1

4 reticulations
score = 703

5 reticulations
score = 527.1

Supplementary File S13: Further discussion of Tablelands rainbowfish diversity and admixture.

Rainbowfish diversity and admixture in the Tablelands

Understanding rainbowfish diversity across the Atherton Tablelands requires studying gene flow between three lineages found in the region. We found evidence of widespread admixture between rainbowfish lineages across the Tablelands, suggesting a complicated history of gene flow. Because we removed sites that had individuals with differing genetic histories from our analyses (i.e., more recent introgression), it is likely that gene flow patterns are even more complex than discussed here. The presence of sampling sites with different genetic histories suggests that interbreeding between species at some locations is recent or ongoing, with allele frequencies not yet evenly spread through populations at any one site.

While we found evidence of gene flow between all pairs of Tablelands lineages, only the Australian aquarium population of *M. eachamensis* was found to have significant admixture proportions of all three. We believe this is due to a breeding event in captivity; female *M. eachamensis* and *M. splendida* are fairly similar and could easily get mixed together by accident. The extant captive population of *M. eachamensis* in Australia is quite small today and has difficulty producing viable offspring, presumably due to high levels of inbreeding. This, combined with admixture from *M. splendida*, may be why the Australian aquarium fish do not look like the original Lake Eacham fish (Tappin, 2011), and this should be noted when considering future breeding or conservation actions. We did not detect any wild populations with significant genetic contribution from all three lineages. This may be due to differences in the timescales of the gene flow events. *Melanotaenia* sp. “Malanda” and *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like” are considered old endemics, and introgressed populations may have emerged a long time ago. By contrast, admixture with *M. splendida* may be more recent. Hybridisation with *M. splendida* is a present and ongoing threat to both *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like” and *M. sp.* “Malanda”, being driven by *M. splendida* range expansions. These range expansions are likely due at least in part to translocations of *M. splendida*,

human disturbance and climate change. The Tablelands has undergone widespread land clearing for agriculture, and the loss of riparian shading combined with climate-augmented increased stream temperatures may be altering instream conditions to be more favourable for *M. splendida* further upstream into higher elevations (Pusey, Bird, Kennard, & Arthington, 1997; Unmack et al., 2016).

Identification of non-admixed populations

We identified populations of non-introgressed *M. sp.* “Malanda” around an unnamed tributary to Thiaki Creek and an unnamed creek at Wallace Road, enabling the description of characteristics and locations of unadmixed populations. This is essential in formally describing this critically endangered species, but difficulties in identifying pure populations have significantly hindered efforts to date. There are multiple admixed *M. sp.* “Malanda”-*M. splendida* populations in the upper North Johnstone system (Figure 2), suggesting that pure *M. sp.* “Malanda” was more widely distributed prior to the appearance of *M. splendida*. We also identified the South Johnstone, Charappa Creek (South Johnstone system) and Lake Euramoo (Barron system) populations as non-introgressed populations of *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like”, which will aid in species description (if *M. eachamensis* is determined to be a separate species from *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like”) or redescription (if the *M. eachamensis* description is invalid and should apply more broadly to *M. sp.* “eachamensis-like”).

References

- Pusey, B. J., Bird, J., Kennard, M. J., & Arthington, A. H. (1997). Distribution of the Lake Eacham rainbowfish in the Wet Tropics region, North Queensland. *Australian Journal of Zoology*, 45(1), 75–84. <https://doi.org/10.1071/ZO96009>
- Tappin, A. (2011). *Rainbowfishes: Their Care & Keeping in Captivity* (2nd editio). Retrieved from <http://rainbowfish.angfaqld.org.au/Book.htm>
- Unmack, P. J., Martin, K., Hammer, M. P., Ebner, B. C., Moy, K., & Brown, C. (2016). Malanda Gold: the tale of a unique rainbowfish from the Atherton Tablelands, now on the verge of extinction. *Fishes Of Sahul*, 30(4), 1039–1054.

Supplementary File S14: Unique variants in Lake Eacham and other populations

Number of silicoDART fixed differences for each individual population when compared to a second sample set comprising all individuals from other sites. This test measures the number of silicoDARTs unique to, or uniquely lost in, each population, i.e., the number of unique variants. The *UV* column represents the number of unique variants observed for each population. The *p-val* column provides a measure of uncertainty around false positives due to finite samples sizes, i.e., the probability that unique variants are present due to sample sizes rather than being a genuine fixed difference. Values were calculated using the *gl.fixed.diff* function from the *dartR* package. This Australian aquarium lineage of *M. eachamensis* was excluded due to its *splendida*-derived genetic signal.

With the exception of the Lake Eacham and Dirran Creek populations, all populations with strong introgression signals (marked with an asterisk) have either no unique variants, or a number of unique variants that may have arisen due to sample sizes ($p > 0.05$). Populations with a significantly non-zero number of unique variants are marked in bold text. The Lake Eacham samples have 8 unique variants, of which 7 are also seen in the European aquarium lineage. Lake Euramoo and Wallace Road, the only two other populations with similar numbers of unique variants to Lake Eacham, are unadmixed populations of *M. sp. "eachamensis-like"* and *M. sp. "Malanda"*. The Little Mulgrave *M. splendida* population may have a high number of unique variants due to being the only population from the Mulgrave River basin in the dataset. This is part of a distinct lowlands lineage of *M. splendida* that is separate from the invasive form in the Tablelands.

Population	species	Sample size	UV	p-val
Charappa Creek	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	1	0.0003
Emu Creek	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	1	0.2729
Gowrie Creek	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	0	0.8941
Lake Euramoo	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	6	0
South Johnstone	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	0	0.8657
Dirran Creek*	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like" – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	5	3	0
Lake Eacham museum samples*	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like" – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	5	8	0
Lake Eacham museum samples + European aquarium lineage*	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like" – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	7	7	0
Gwynne Creek*	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like" – M. splendida</i>	8	0	0.6816
Spider Creek*	<i>M. sp. "eachamensis-like" – M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.8332

Molo Creek tributary	<i>M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	15	0	0.5435
Thiaki Creek tributary	<i>M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	15	0	0.6104
Wallace Road	<i>M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	20	12	0
Molo Creek & tributary *	<i>M. sp. "Malanda" – M. splendida</i>	10	0	0.5932
Thiaki Creek*	<i>M. sp. "Malanda" – M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.9704
Williams Creek East	<i>M. sp. "Malanda" – M. splendida</i>	26	0	0.5738
Williams Creek East 2*	<i>M. sp. "Malanda" – M. splendida</i>	17	0	0.7039
Barney Springs	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.9628
Beatrice River	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.8959
Cleminson Creek	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.6793
Gillies Creek	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.7358
Little Mulgrave	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	15	0.3234
Middle Brook	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.9942
Tinaroo	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.9052
Upper Rocky Creek	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.9015
Victoria Creek	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	1	0.7232
Wallace Road lower	<i>M. splendida</i>	5	0	0.7618
Nicholas Creek*	<i>M. splendida – M. sp. "eachamensis-like"</i>	5	1	0.9316
Battle Creek*	<i>M. splendida – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	5	0	0.7274
Imrie Creek*	<i>M. splendida – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	5	2	0.9552
Short Creek*	<i>M. splendida – M. sp. "Malanda"</i>	5	0	0.7433

Coverage of unique variants in the Lake Eacham and Lake Euramoo populations. The extinct Lake Eacham population had eight unique variants – seven restriction sites which were not found in any other sample (highlighted in green), and one which was absent in Lake Eacham but present in every other sample (highlighted in grey). Coverage at these restriction sites was good, with only one NA in the wild population and one at a different site in an aquarium specimen. Presence-absence results were congruent between the museum specimens and the aquarium lineage at all but one restriction site.

Lake Euramoo’s population has six unique variants: five restrictions sites not found in any other sample (highlighted in green) and one site absent in Lake Euramoo but present in all other wild population samples (highlighted in grey). One aquarium specimen also lacks this restriction site (highlighted in orange), but is the only sample in our dataset to do so other than the Euramoo population. This absent restriction site may be due to a loss of genetic diversity in captivity.

Specimen	Population	Restriction site presence(1)/absence(0)													
RFEachQM.1	Lake Eacham museum specimens	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
RFEachQM.2	Lake Eacham museum specimens	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
RFEachQM.3	Lake Eacham museum specimens	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
RFEachQM.4	Lake Eacham museum specimens	0	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
RFEachQM.5	Lake Eacham museum specimens	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	0	0	0	0	0
MEEuro.1	<i>M. eachamensis</i> European aquarium lineage	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	NA	0	0	0	0	0
MEEuro.2	<i>M. eachamensis</i> European aquarium lineage	0	1	1	NA	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
RF1820.1	Lake Euramoo <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like”	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	NA	1	1	1	1	1
RF1820.2	Lake Euramoo <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like”	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	NA	1	1
RF1820.3	Lake Euramoo <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like”	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	NA	1	1	1	1	1
RF1820.4	Lake Euramoo <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like”	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	1	1	1	1
RF1820.5	Lake Euramoo <i>M. sp.</i> “eachamensis-like”	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	NA	NA